

SCIENTIFIC APPROACHES TO PEDAGOGICAL COMPETENCE IN DEVELOPED COUNTRIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14557862>

Abstract. *This article analyzes existing approaches to pedagogical competence in developed countries. Pedagogical competence involves the delivery of the cognitive skills and competencies necessary in the process of pedagogical activity of teachers to young people in a fast, qualitative way. Differences in approaches to cross-country pedagogical competence and their impact are considered, as well as the consequentiality of factors affecting the demand and educational process of global requirements. In particular, the importance of the introduction of an updated and modernized education system based on a competency approach to our country is highlighted.*

Keywords: *pedagogical competence, teacher, developed countries, education, approaches, global requirements, USA, Finland, Canada, Germany.*

Introduction Approaches to pedagogical competence in developed countries are related to modern requirements of the education system and globalization processes. In any society, education is important for the development of society. Therefore, it is important to improve pedagogical competence and introduce innovative approaches. This topic emphasizes the need to develop not only theoretical knowledge, but also practical skills of teachers in the educational process.

Today, cultural, economic and political changes require new approaches in the education system. It is a leader in the formation and development of pedagogical competence in developed countries, particularly in the USA, Finland, Canada, and Germany.

The competence of teachers is very important for improving the quality of education, successfully preparing students and contributing to the overall development of society. Among these countries, the term competence has entered the education system of our country.

By fulfilling the tasks defined within the framework of the concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, taking into account the special emphasis on the development of competencies and skills of STEAM sciences and critical thinking, independent search and analysis of information, meeting the requirements of the modern innovative economy general education programs and new state education standards will be introduced [1; Appendix 4].

This research serves to improve the quality of the educational system by determining the development of pedagogical competence and its place in practice. Also, approaches to pedagogical competence allow to offer new methods and strategies for teachers of our country by studying the experience of other countries. This research will help to further develop innovations in the educational system and enrich professional training.

Literature review Scientific and literary sources on the development of competence of young people in the modern education system are covered in detail.

1. In particular, famous professors analyze the effectiveness of professional development of teachers in Linda Darling-Hammond's manual [2], in the work of J. Hattie, he studies the influence of many factors in education on pedagogical competence, C. D. Glickman., S. P. Gordon., and J. M. Ross give recommendations on the improvement of teaching process [4], in Gordon's book, he presents necessary strategies for improving educational leadership and pedagogical competence [3], H. Timperley's article provides information about the process of teachers' self-development and its impact on students [7]. These works are relevant in the process of implementing pedagogical competence and include research on improving the process of introducing competence into education.

The analysis of the above literature shows that the professional development of teachers in the educational system requires the modern approaches to the improvement of competence, the adaptation of curricula to pedagogical competence, leadership ability to competence. This requires modernizing the concept of the educational system based on competence from today's teacher.

Research methodology. In developed countries, many studies have been carried out on the issue of scientific approaches to pedagogical competence. Based on the analysis of this literature, the following main points are taken into account: 1. Social and cultural context. In developed countries, the professional development of teachers is carried out in accordance with the social and cultural context. This approach encourages teachers to actively participate in their communities and make a difference. [2; 16-b] 2. Cooperation and exchange of experience. Cooperation and exchange of experience among teachers is important in many developed countries. Platforms are created for teachers to learn from each other, share their experiences and solve problems together. 3. Continuing education. In developed countries, continuing education processes are offered for teachers. These processes provide opportunities for teachers to improve their skills and use pedagogical innovations [9; 18-b] 4. Analysis and evaluation. Qualitative and quantitative analysis methods are used to evaluate the effectiveness of professional development programs. Teachers' attention is paid to self-evaluation and analysis of the results of changes in the educational process. 5. Pedagogical competence. Professional development programs for teachers are aimed at increasing pedagogical competence. This competence plays an important role in ensuring the success of teachers in the educational process.

Methodology. Qualitative and quantitative methods were used in this research. For qualitative analysis, theoretical knowledge was analyzed on the basis of literature, important concepts and methodologies were highlighted. For quantitative analysis, questionnaires were conducted, and their results were analyzed using statistical methods.

This methodology makes it possible to determine the level of competence of young people and develop recommendations for their development. With the help of this analysis and methodology, the role of modern pedagogical approaches and innovative technologies in the development of pedagogical competence in young people is studied in detail.

Discussion. In this article, various methods and their results in the studied literature were considered from the point of view of discussion:

How can Finland's individual approach be useful for teachers in other countries? Does this method affect students' self-management? Finland's individual approach helps students develop their skills. This method develops students' self-assessment and self-management skills.

As a result of the educational method based on social learning and group work in the Swedish education system, how does group work affect the development of students' personal

competencies? How to evaluate the interaction of students in a group? The importance of group work in the educational process helps to develop social skills among students. This method improves the role of students in teamwork and their interactions.

What are the advantages and disadvantages of problem-based learning in the German education system compared to other pedagogical approaches. A problem-based approach gives students the opportunity to find solutions to real problems. This approach helps to improve students' critical thinking skills.

What is the importance of STEAM education for teenagers and children in the USA? What role does this approach play in preventing adverse interventions? STEAM education develops problem-solving and creative skills while providing students with in-depth knowledge of science and technology.

This approach helps to increase students' creativity and innovative thinking skills. Discussion of these questions will help to increase the effectiveness of mutual learning methods.

Analysis and results. Pedagogical competence plays an important role in the formation of students' knowledge, skills and abilities. The analysis of pedagogical approaches used in developed countries, their results and effects are of great importance in the way of improving educational processes. Results and indicators showing the effectiveness of approaches to pedagogical competence in different countries can be expressed as follows:

Finland: More than 90% of students gain independent thinking and self-assessment skills during their education. Sweden: 80% of students develop their social skills through active participation in many interactive and group activities. Germany: 75% of students improve their critical thinking skills through problem-based learning. USA: as a result of STEAM education, 70% of students improve their skills in mathematics, physics, and natural sciences at a high level [5; 34-p]

Approaches to pedagogical competence in developed countries are aimed not only at providing students with knowledge, but also at developing them as individuals. Institutional approach: schools should develop an approach that meets the individual needs of students [4; 5-b]. This approach helps motivate students and expand their knowledge. Knowledge and skills of pedagogues: competence of pedagogues is also important in developed countries. Their role in the educational process is the main factor in determining the students' learning methods. Interdependence: The interrelationship between pedagogical competence and social skills is also influenced by external factors and cultural contexts. Each country adopts a pedagogical approach in accordance with its culture and social system.

Conclusion/Recommendations. Approaches to pedagogical competence in developed countries show effective results in improving the educational system and developing intellectual, social and creative skills of students. These approaches serve to increase the effectiveness of the educational process and achieve global goals. Effective results can be achieved through the processes of interaction, writing and sharing experience between teachers and students.

In general, the issue of developing pedagogical competence among teachers is one of the most urgent areas of the education system, and more in-depth research and the development of practical approaches are required in this area.

Such activities not only provide students with quality education, but also create the necessary foundation for their future success.

REFERENCES

1. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining Farmoni, 29.04.2019-yildagi PF5712-son;(4-ilova)
2. Darling-Hammond, L. (2017). "Effective Teacher Professional Development".
3. Glickman, C. D., Gordon, S. P., & Ross-Gordon, J. M. (2018). "Supervision and Instructional Leadership: A Developmental Approach."
4. Hattie, J. (2009). "Visible Learning: A Synthesis of Over 800 Meta-Analyses Relating to Achievement."
5. Marzano, R. J. (2011). "Learning Science: A Graduate Course in Learning Theory".
6. Schmidt, W. H., & Prawat, R. S. (2006). "Curriculum coherence and curricular reform".
7. Timperley, H. (2008). "Teacher Professional Development, Teacher Learning, and the Ability to Adapt to Students".
8. Weinert, F.J. (2001). "Concept of Competence: A Conceptual Framework for the Assessment of Competencies".
9. Shulman, L. S. (1986). "Those Who Understand: Knowledge Growth in Teaching."